

A Comparative Assessment of Fuzzy logic and PID controllers in Two wheeled self balancing robot

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Abstract— This paper provides a comparative assessment between the performance of Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) and Fuzzy logic based controller (FLC) implemented in Two Wheeled Self-Balancing Robot (TWSBR). Both the controllers are testified and studied through real time simulation in MATLAB Simulink environment. This analysis validates the successful implementation of both controllers for controlling the linear position and tilt angle of the robot. Through simulation it has been observed that the fuzzy logic controller shows better results in terms of settling time as compared to PID controller.

Keywords-Fuzzylogic, Proportional-integral-derivative, Simulation, TWSBR

I. INTRODUCTION

Two wheeled self-balancing Robot (TWSBR) has made an outstanding breakthrough in the field of robotics and its application can be seen in various platforms like transport system and walking of humanoid robot. In last two decades, researchers have shown deep interests in the controlling of two wheeled balancing mobile robots. Mechanical stability, being the important challenge of this robot, requires a competent controller. PID controller is commendably implemented for balancing such robot pertaining to its simplicity [1-4]. Other linear controllers like partial feedback linearization method [5-6], linear quadratic regulator [7] and pole placement control [8-9] are also being employed as control strategy in TWSBR. In reality, TWSBR are inherently unstable and highly non-linear systems. While using the controller like PID, several assumptions are made for establishing the dynamic model of TWSBR to make it linear. These assumptions neglect some dynamic parameters which will affect the functioning of TWSBR. The functioning of linear controller can be improved by proper tuning of controller performance parameters that requires human expert knowledge. In recent times, with the advancement of intelligent control system, Artificial intelligent methodology like Genetic Algorithm, fuzzy logic, Neural Network etc. are on board to be used in control of balancing robot. The Artificial intelligent control system becomes the obvious choice to deal with highly nonlinear system like TWSBR. Among these AI techniques fuzzy logic is quite popular because of its ability to put on the expert knowledge through simple scheming in form of linguistic variables [10]. The fuzzy logic system has shown better dynamic functioning [11] for the control of self-balancing robot. This paper highlights the comparative assessment

between fuzzy logic based controller and PID (proportional-integral-derivative) controller used for controlling two wheel self-balancing robot. The real-time simulations of these controllers are conducted rigorously in the MATLAB Simulink environment. The maximum overshoot and settling time taken by both the controllers are compared at last.

II. ROBOT SYSTEM MODELLING

The basic control strategy of any two wheeled balancing robot system follows the dynamic modelling of inverted pendulum balancing scheme. The system consists of pendulum with mass m which is placed inverted on the moving cart (fig. 1). The force exerted in the cart prevents the pendulum to fall down and makes the system stable.

Fig. 1. Inverted Pendulum balancing system

The dynamic model of inverted pendulum (also used in later simulation process) is represented by following differential equation (1, 2)

$$\ddot{\theta} = \frac{-(M + m)g \sin \theta + \cos \theta (F + m\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \theta - b\dot{x})}{I[M \cos^2 \theta - (M + m)]} \quad (1)$$

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{mg \sin \theta \cos \theta - (F + m\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \theta - b\dot{x})}{m \cos^2 \theta - (M + m)} \quad (2)$$

F is applied force for balancing pendulum having length l and mass moment of inertia I . M and m is the mass of cart and pendulum respectively, and the friction coefficient for the cart is b . x and θ are the system variables representing cart position and pendulum angle from vertical axis respectively.

III. CONTROL DESIGN

The self-balancing robot, which is inherently unstable system, has primarily two control units: Position Control and Angle control. The angle control unit maintains the vertical angular position at 0° while the position control unit obtains the desire linear position of TWMR. This section gives a detail description of the two control strategies: fuzzy logic based control system and conventional PID controller, used in the TWSBR.

A. PID controller

The PID control system, as shown in the equation (3), consists of three parts: proportional (P), integral (I), and differential (D). This feedback controller primarily aims at reducing error (e) between set value (SV) and process variable measured through sensors (PV).

$$u = K_p e + K_i \int e dt + K_d \frac{de}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Where u is the control action and K_p , K_i and K_d are gain factors of Proportional, Integral and Derivative terms respectively. The proportional factor (K_p) lessens the rising time but can never eradicate steady-state error. The integral part (K_i) is added to deal with the steady-state error, despite providing worse transient response. The derivative term (K_d) maintains the stability by reducing the overshoot and progressing the transient response. In our experiment we use two PID controllers one each for position and tilt angle control (Fig. 2), where the output is the control force and inputs are position and tilt angle errors. The proportional term of PID algorithm increases the control force power, increasing this term leads to oscillation and lower valve increases response time. So, the differential term act as a damper for reducing the oscillation produced by K_p .

Fig. 2. Block diagram of PID controller used in TWSBR

B. Fuzzy logic controller

This controller is purely based on concept of fuzzy set theory proposed by Lotfi Aliasker Zadeh. The entire process in this controller is performed through linguistic expression that gives rise to simple control scheme. Here, we design the control algorithm in simple linguistic form: “If angle is zero then the force is zero”. The fuzzy logic based control system is composed of three elementary stages:

- Representing input (crisp value) in terms of fuzzy linguistic language (Fuzzy sets and membership functions).
- Computation of the fuzzy output from fuzzy rule base. This stage is engaged for the construction of the control algorithm i.e. fuzzy rule that will give the output.
- Defuzzification of fuzzy value to specific output values (crisp valve).

Fig. 3. Block diagram of fuzzy controller used in TWSBR

Two fuzzy based controllers are used for position and tilt angle control (Fig. 3). The angle controller has two inputs (Tilt angle and Tilt angle rate having range of $[-3, 3]$ and $[-2, 2]$ respectively) and one output signal (force having range of $[-10, 10]$). Similarly, the position controller has two inputs (distance and distance rate both having range of $[-3, 3]$ respectively) and one output signal (force having range of $[-10, 10]$). The following fuzzy sets and triangular membership function (Fig. 3 and 4) is assigned for the both input and output of position and tilt angle controller.

The fuzzy sets used for control input(s) and output(s) are abbreviated as NVB: Negatively Very Big, NB: Negatively Big, NS: Negatively Small, NE: Neutral, PS: Positively Small, PB: Positively Big, PVB: Positively Very Big.

(a)

Fig. 4. Membership functions for (a) tilt angle and (b) tilt angle rate and (c) Force output.

Fig. 5 Membership functions for (a) Distance and (b) Distance rate and (c) Force output.

IV. SIMULATION ANALYSIS AND RESULT

This section overviews the real time simulation of the proposed Fuzzy and PID controller in Matlab Simulink. The rule base for two fuzzy controllers is shown in the Table. I and II.

TABLE I. Fuzzy Rule Base for Position Control

Position	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB
Position rate							
NVB	NVB	NVB	NVB	NVB	NB	NS	NE
NB	NVB	NVB	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS
NS	NVB	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB
NE	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB
PS	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB	PB
PB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB	PVB	PVB
PVB	NE	PS	PB	PVB	PVB	PVB	PVB

TABLE II. Fuzzy Rule Base for Tilt Angle Control

Angle	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB
Angle rate							
NVB	NVB	NVB	NVB	NVB	NB	NS	NE
NB	NVB	NVB	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS
NS	NVB	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB
NE	NVB	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB
PS	NB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB	PB
PB	NS	NE	PS	PB	PVB	PVB	PVB
PVB	NE	PS	PB	PVB	PVB	PVB	PVB

The output (controlling force) of position and tilt angle controller is summed up in both fuzzy and PID controller. The

Reference values of position and tilt angle are set 0.2 and 0 respectively. It is imperative to select proper gain factor in PID controller. These values are found to be:

For Position controller

$$K_p = 2.55, K_i = 0.005 \text{ and } K_d = 0.005$$

For Tilt angle controller

$$K_p = 50, K_i = 35 \text{ and } K_d = 8.$$

The controller performance can be seen from the responses of tilt angle and position with respect to time derived from the simulation experiment (Fig. 5 and 6). Both figures exhibit the comparison between the step responses of Tilt angle and Distance for both fuzzy (Blue color) and PID controller (Red color). The settling time and maximum overshoot for both the controller is shown in the Table. III.

Table III. Comparative Evaluation of controllers (tilt angle)

Controller	Settling Time (sec)	Max. overshoot (radian)
PID	8.2	0.009
Fuzzy logic Controller	5	0.07

Fig.5. Position response

Fig.6. Tilt Angle response

V. CONCLUSION

The foremost objective of this paper is to compare the performance of PID and Fuzzy controller for controlling the position and tilt angle of two wheeled self-balancing robot. It is apparent from the results of simulation that both the controllers have capability to be used for robot control. However, Fuzzy logic controller showed better performance by using less settling time for obtaining desired angle and position. Further Improvement is required in both controllers for reducing the maximum overshoot. This could be done through proper tuning of the controller parameters.

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